

Comparative evaluation of the compressive behaviour of modular composite wall with and without sheathing

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Introduction

Modular building construction

- Pre-fabrication of structural members in a factory and then transported to the site for assembly to construct a building
- Quick construction process, better quality, low capital investment and less environmental impact

Holiday Inn Express, Manchester, UK
(Chapman 2017)

Material of construction

- Conventional materials such as Steel & light steel, concrete and timber

Steel containers modular building
(Howick 2020)

Timber concrete
(Ferdous et al. 2019)

Concrete core modular building
(Ferdous et al. 2019)

Drawbacks of conventional materials

- Steel: **Corrosion, heavy weight and high maintenance cost** (Ferdous et al. 2019)
- Concrete: **Prone to cracking during transportation, heavy weight** (Lacey et al. 2018)
- Timber: **Pest and biological decay** (Ferdous & Manalo 2014)

Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) as construction material

- High strength-to-weight ratio
- Design flexibility
- Zero corrosion
- Very less maintenance
- Immunity from pest and biological decay

FRP composite wall system

- Modular wall system need to withstand sustained and operational loads.
- Type of loads acting on wall system (Compression, In-plane shear and uniform distributed load)

Composite wall system

General configuration
of wall system

GFRP RHS 100x75x5 (mm)

GFRP sheathing 2400x600x6.5(mm)

Full scale compression test
(2400x600mm)

Material characterisation- GFRP RHS

Full profile test

Axial compression

Transverse compression

(a) Stress vs strain

(b) Axial failure

(c) Transverse failure

Source: (Sharda et al. 2021)

Material characterisation- GFRP Sheathing

Coupon testing

(a) Tension- Longitudinal
(Instant delamination)

(b) Tension- Transverse
(Resin cracking)

(c) Compression- Longitudinal
(Crushing failure)

(d) Compression- Transverse
(Interfibre fracture failure)

Source: (Sharda et al. 2021)

Full scale compression test

GFRP wall panel
without sheathing

Frame only

Horizontal cracking

Junction failure

GFRP wall panel with
GFRP sheathing

Sheathed frame

Inter-laminar delamination
& Junction failure

Debonding

Source: (Sharda et al. 2021)

FEA- Frame only

Ultimate compression stress limit

Horizontal cracking

Source: (Sharda et al. 2021)

Full scale FEA for extended studs frame only

End crushing

1. 10.63 times higher overall stiffness
2. 11.91 times loading capacity

Source: (Sharda et al. 2021)

Conclusion

- Material characterisation of full profile is quick, repeatable and helps in understanding constituent material's failure behaviour.
- Linear finite element analysis provides agreement with the experimental results.
- Significant increment in axial stiffness and loading capacity can be achieved by altering frame configuration.
- Finite element analysis of combined loading conditions such as compression and flexural load or compression and shear load should be conducted to understand the behaviour of wall system under combined loading conditions.

References

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Thank you for your kind attention

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Research papers

1. Axial compression behaviour of all-composite modular wall system

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0263822321004463>

2. Flexural behaviour of composite modular wall systems under uniformly distributed and concentrated loads

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263822322010789>

3. In-plane shear behaviour of prefabricated modular wall system assembled of fibre reinforced polymer composites

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214509522009512>